

A NOVEL APPROACH FOR THE ESTIMATION OF THE BRAKE FRICTION COEFFICIENT FOR ENVIRONMENTAL AND SAFETY CONTROL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The increased use of disc brakes on passenger cars, along with the increasing stiffening of regulations on safety and emission reduction, has led the research world to focus on the prediction of brake performance and wear under different working conditions. Therefore, a proper tool is demanded to monitor the brake operation and to increase the performance of control systems such as ABS, TC and ESP by supplying an accurate estimate of the brake torque. In addition, it could be used to support a brake controller aimed at minimizing the wear volume and reducing the emissions of fine particles. Another application that has given rise to noticeable interest among the control community is the vehicle electrification. The electric vehicles demand the design of new controllers to handle the regenerative brake and to enable the blending function with conventional brakes. The mentioned controllers require the estimation of physical quantities that are not directly measurable through the already existing on-board sensors. In accordance with these needs, a state observer based on the linear Kalman filter is presented in this paper. The proposed observer provides an estimation of the vehicle hub torque and, therefore, of the brake friction coefficient encompassing the chassis and wheels rotational dynamics and relying upon the vehicle sensors signals. Such a tool is able to achieve the abovementioned goals by improving the driving safety, during emergency braking, and enhancing the actuation during service braking.

INTRODUCTION

The increasingly stiffening of regulations on driving safety [1] and emission reduction leads both the academy and industry to devise innovative solutions aimed at enhancing the environmental friendliness of new vehicles. It is expectable that, in accordance with this trend, in few years also the non-exhaust emissions from the vehicles will be regulated. Indeed, a review of the Institute for Energy and Transport of the European Commission reports that the PM10 brake wear emission from passenger cars rates up to 8.8 mg/km [2] exceeding the limit of 5 mg/km set for diesel engines exhaust emissions. Hence, friction brakes and tires are nowadays considered as the main emitters of micro- and nano-particles in road vehicles next to the internal combustion engines [3].

This new trend has given rise to a great interest from the brake and control community in developing new devices and control systems aimed at abating the non-exhaust emissions and enhancing the braking performance [4], [5]. In addition, the vehicle electrification requires the implementation of new control systems able to handle the regenerative blending functions [6]. Therefore, it is expectable that a tool able to estimate the hub torque and the friction coefficient is of course useful to improve the safety and the environmental friendliness of modern conventional and electric vehicles.

Unfortunately, a large set of phenomena occurring between the brake pad and disc affects the brake effectiveness and make its operation awkward to render through classical model based approach or neural networks. Brake fading [7], [8], brake bedding [9], brake hysteresis against the pressure [10], brake hysteresis against the speed [11], brake wear [12] and aging [9], dependence on the environmental conditions [13] are phenomena that affect the dynamics of the pad-disc contact causing a wide variation of the friction coefficient. It is experimentally assessed that the friction coefficient can range between 0.3 and 0.6 [14], [15] with peaks up to 0.8 and down to 0.1 [7], [16]. Just few models have been developed and used for the automotive brake friction prediction without obtaining satisfactory results. The bulk of the proposed models are only suitable to describe the common pin-disc contact in a controlled environment [17] and therefore are inadequate to render the automotive brake pad-disc interface.

In the present work, a hub-torque observer based on the linear Kalman filter is proposed with the aim of estimating the brake friction coefficient. The Kalman filter is widely used as states observer because it ensures good robustness for tolerating differences between models and real dynamics of the vehicle, variations of model parameters and signal errors. Successively, the developed observer is tuned and tested against a reference vehicle model from the proprietary software IPG CarMaker 4.0. Preliminary results make the state observation approach a promising solution for the estimation of the brake friction coefficient.

VEHICLE DYNAMICS STATE AND HUB TORQUE ESTIMATION

Linear Kalman filter

The KF is defined as the minimum variance state estimator for linear dynamic systems with Gaussian noise. It is a tool that combines information coming from models (prediction step) and sensors (update step) in presence of uncertainty in order to provide an estimation of system state variables. The present work will not dwell upon the mathematical subtleties of the Kalman theory; herein it is only worth reporting the general equation of a linear filter. For the prediction phase:

$$\hat{x}_k = F_k \hat{x}_{k-1} + B_k u_k \quad (1)$$

$$P_k = F_k P_{k-1} F_k^T + Q_k \quad (2)$$

where, for the discrete state space formulation of equations (1) and (2), \hat{x}_k represents the observed state vector at time step k , obtained from the previous best estimate; u_k is simply the input vector. F_k is the state matrix and represents the process model ruling the dependence between the states at increasing time step, B_k is the input matrix that distributes the input among the states; P_k is the covariance matrix of the state updated with the best previous estimate; Q_k represents the uncertainty that is attributed to the model of the system. The eq. (1) and (2) are liable for the information content of the model predicted part of the Kalman filter; the estimation of the state vector and its covariance matrix are performed by using the available information at the time step $(k - 1)$ to feed the predictive model. Instead, the general equations for the measurement update are:

$$K' = P_k H_k^T (H_k P_k H_k^T + R_k)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

$$\hat{x}'_k = \hat{x}_k + K' (z_k - H_k \hat{x}_k) \quad (4)$$

$$P'_k = P_k - K' H_k P_k \quad (5)$$

The superscript means that both the state vector and its covariance matrix encompass the sensors information. K' represents the Kalman gain; the output matrix H_k represents the measurement model that ties the state vector \hat{x}_k to the measurements z_k ; R_k represents the uncertainty that is attributed to the sensors, generally linked to the white noise. Hence, the update step consists into comparing the real output z_k with the estimated output $H_k\hat{x}_k$ in order to correct the state vector.

It is worth remarking that particular attention must be given to the filter initialization: the initial state vector \hat{x}_0 and the initial state covariance matrix P_0 affect the convergence rate of the linear filter. Moreover, the matrixes of the process noise covariance Q_k and the measurement noise covariance R_k are the filter tuning parameters. These latter must be calibrated in order to give more importance to the prediction part or to the update part, depending on the quality of the model and measurements. For example, the more Q_k is high, the more the sensors output will lead the results because, as can be seen from eq. (3), the more the KF relies on the measurements.

Observer for hub torque - $O_{T_{hub}}$

In the last years, the state observation technique has been largely applied in the automotive field as a valid substitute to the model-based approach. The literature research effort has mainly focused on the fields of observation of the tire-road friction coefficient [18], [19], [20] and direct observation of the tire forces [21], [22]. For these methods, available sensors on cars are used to estimate tire/road information based on the wheel and vehicle dynamic state variables. The bulk of the literature instances assumes the hub torque as an input of the state equations; instead, for the matter here presented, it constitutes one of the states to observe in order to estimate the friction coefficient. Consequently, the state space formulation associated to the observer is rearranged in order to handle the hub torque as an augmented state [23]. The noise of both the input variables and the sensors take a toll on the observation capability. Hence, an accurate model of the vehicle dynamics and a smart handling of the sensor signals is required to preserve the estimation quality. From now on, the i index will be used to identify the four tyres: fl, fr, rl, rr .

Figure 1. Sketch of the proposed linear hub-torque observer $O_{T_{hub}}$: the update part is based on the measurements coming from the hub sensors (ω_i) and chassis accelerometers (a_x, a_y); the prediction part relies on the wheels dynamics equations and on the tire model that, in turn, requires the tire slip coefficients ($\hat{s}_{Li}, \hat{s}_{Si}$) and the vertical load (F_{Zi}).

Figure 2. System of forces acting on the wheel and ruling the wheel rotational dynamics. The meaning of the variables is specified within the text.

The state-space formulation associated with the observer stems from a quarter-car model for the vehicle longitudinal and lateral dynamics with fixed parameters. With reference to Figure 1, the proposed tool relies on the signals coming from the chassis accelerometer and the hub sensors, reported as blue blocks, and on three units, represented as orange blocks.

1) The wheel rotational dynamics is illustrated in Figure 2 and rendered by the eq. (6):

$$I_\omega \dot{\omega}_i = T_{hub_i} - R_{L_i} - F_{L_i} r_\omega \quad (6)$$

ω_i represents the wheel speed, I_ω is the wheel inertia and r_ω is the wheel radius; T_{hub_i} is the torque exerted on the wheel hub; R_{L_i} is the wheel rolling resistance; F_{L_i} is the wheel longitudinal force; F_{ai} and N_i constitute the ground-contact components, namely the friction force and normal reaction.

- 2) The longitudinal component of the force acting on the wheel (F_{L_i}) is evaluated as a function of the wheel slips (\dot{s}_{Li} , \dot{s}_{Si}) and the vertical forces (F_{Zi}). For a better understanding of the equation, please refer to the Burckhardt tyre model in [24]. The vertical wheel loads and the slip ratios are observed in accordance with the methodologies reported respectively in [25] and [24].
- 3) The virtual sensor estimates the chassis longitudinal (F_x^{vs}) and lateral (F_y^{vs}) forces by drawing upon the measured longitudinal (a_x) and lateral (a_y) accelerations in accordance with the following eq. (7) and (8):

$$F_x^{vs} = m_v a_x - F_{R_x} \quad (7)$$

$$F_y^{vs} = m_v a_y \quad (8)$$

where, m_v is the mass of the vehicle and F_{R_x} is the sum of the forces opposing to the vehicle motion, namely the rolling resistance and the air drag force. At last, once the hub torque has been observed, the estimation of the brake friction coefficient is easily achievable: (i) the signal from the brake pressure sensor is used to evaluate the clamping force; (ii) the radial clamping force application point is known and assumed constant.

Estimation process

The filter state, measurement and input vectors are defined in eq. (9)-(11) and the dynamics of the state variables are derived in compliance with the set of eq. (12a)-(12d) as follows:

$$x_k = \{\omega_{i,k}, \dot{\omega}_{i,k}, F_{L_{i,k}}, T_{hub_{i,k}}\}_{16 \times 1}^T \quad (9)$$

$$z_k = \{\omega_{i,k}^s, F_{L_{i,k}}^{vs}\}_{8 \times 1}^T \quad (10)$$

$$u_k = \{\dot{F}_{L_{i,k}}\}_{4 \times 1}^T \quad (11)$$

$$\left\{ \begin{array}{l} \omega_{i,k+1} = \omega_{i,k} + \Delta t \cdot \dot{\omega}_{i,k} \\ \dot{\omega}_{i,k+1} = \frac{T_{hub_{i,k}} - F_{L_{i,k}} r_\omega}{I_\omega} \\ F_{L_{i,k+1}} = F_{L_{i,k}} + \Delta t \cdot \underbrace{\dot{F}_{L_{i,k}}}_{input} \\ T_{hub_{i,k+1}} = T_{hub_{i,k}} \end{array} \right. \quad (12a)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} \dot{\omega}_{i,k+1} = \frac{T_{hub_{i,k}} - F_{L_{i,k}} r_\omega}{I_\omega} \end{array} \right\} \quad (12b)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} F_{L_{i,k+1}} = F_{L_{i,k}} + \Delta t \cdot \underbrace{\dot{F}_{L_{i,k}}}_{input} \end{array} \right\} \quad (12c)$$

$$\left. \begin{array}{l} T_{hub_{i,k+1}} = T_{hub_{i,k}} \end{array} \right\} \quad (12d)$$

The previous system of equations represents the process model in discrete time formulation where Δt is the small discrete time step. For the convenience's sake of the analytical representation, the rolling resistance is included in the longitudinal tyre force. The hub speed of each wheel $\omega_{i,k}$, is updated through (12a) once its derivative $\dot{\omega}_i$ is known from the wheel dynamics of eq.(12b). The Burckardt tire model, in compliance with (12c), provides the longitudinal tyre force $F_{L_{i,k}}$. At last, in (12d), a random walk approach is used for the hub torque state $T_{hub_{i,k}}$; it will be then corrected in the update phase.

With reference to the output vector used for the update phase, ω_i^s is the hub sensors measurement for each wheel, instead $F_{L_i}^{vs}$ represents the virtually sensed longitudinal force on each wheel obtained from eq. (7) by exploiting the longitudinal accelerometer signal. Hereunto, two issues become known:

- eq. (7) provides a single value of longitudinal force acting on the entire vehicle;
- the virtually-sensed and model-predicted components of the tyre force reside in two different reference systems, respectively the chassis-accelerometer and the tyre-model (Figure 3).

In order to solve the first problem, the eq. (13) and (14) are applied:

$$F_{x_i}^{vs} = \gamma_i(F_{z_i}) \cdot F_x^{vs} \quad (13)$$

$$F_{y_i}^{vs} = \gamma_i(F_{z_i}) \cdot F_y^{vs} \quad (14)$$

The longitudinal and lateral forces are distributed on each wheel by means of the γ_i parameter, proportional to the vertical load F_{z_i} . In the second instance, the virtually sensed and predicted longitudinal components of the tyre force must be moved to the same reference to perform a correct observation. For simplicity reasons, the wheel reference is chosen as the target. As shown in the Figure 3, the sideslip angle α_i and the steering angle δ must be taken into account to rotate the virtually sensed force to the wheel reference. Hence, the translation matrix $\bar{A}(\alpha_i, \delta)$ is defined and the following relation is stated:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} F_{L_i}^{vs} \\ F_{S_i}^{vs} \end{Bmatrix} = \bar{A}(\alpha_i, \delta) \begin{Bmatrix} F_{x_i}^{vs} \\ F_{y_i}^{vs} \end{Bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

Please, refer to [24] for the associated analytical formulation.

Observability analysis

This section provides the reader with a brief description concerning the observability matrix and observability condition with reference to the previously defined linear system. In order to assess the latter condition for the defined observer, it is necessary that the observability matrix $O_{T_{hub}}$ has rank equal to the number of the state of the system. By comparing the equations (1)-(5) with (12a)-(12d) it is possible to defined the matrices of the state F and of the output H . If N is the size of the state vector, the observation matrix is defined as follows:

Figure 3. Illustration of the reference systems mentioned in the text. The reference translation from the chassis (x-y) to the wheel (L-S) encompasses the steering angle δ and the side slip angle α_i .

$$O_{T_{hub}} = [H \ HF \ HF^2 \ HF^3 \ \dots \ HF^{N-1}]^T \quad (16)$$

Using the function $obsrv(F, H)$ and $rank(O_{T_{hub}})$ from the Matlab software, it is possible to verify that $O_{T_{hub}}$ has full rank.

MODEL SIMULATION

In the next section, the hub torque observer is assessed against a reference model developed in IPG CarMaker 4.0. The IPG CarMaker proprietary software models and renders the dynamic behaviour of vehicles moving on different types of roads. It also consists of a big database of vehicles and driving manoeuvres to choose from. The CarMaker software includes aerodynamic forces, a very simple engine model, powertrain with manual transmission, nonlinear suspension model, steering system, braking system with ABS. With reference to the simulation, a compact car is selected and the Pacejka Magic formula tire model [26] is employed to depict the road-vehicle contact forces with effectiveness and low computational burden. The vehicle parameters are shown in the following table where m_s is the vehicle sprung mass, I_z is the yaw inertia, i_1 to i_5 are the gear ratios of the transmission, i_{diff} is the differential ratio, h_{cg} is the height of the center of gravity, $K_{br,f}$ and $K_{br,r}$ are the braking constants for the front and rear brakes ruling the generated brake friction against the actuated pressure.

Parameter	Value	Parameter	Value
m_v	1463 kg	i_3	1,35
m_s	1301 kg	i_4	1,05
I_z	1800 kg m ²	i_5	0,8
I_ω	1 kg m ²	i_{diff}	4,1
r_ω	0,31 m	h_{cg}	0,58 m
i_1	3,4	$K_{br,f}$	161 Nm/MPa
i_2	1,9	$K_{br,r}$	77 Nm/MPa

Table 1. Vehicle parameters used for the simulation

Validation and Results

The proposed Kalman filter has been adapted to the vehicle model in order to assess its prediction capability. The IPG CarMaker environment has been used to simulate two distinct manoeuvres, namely a straight line braking and a turning manoeuvre, whose acceleration profiles and trajectories are reported in the Figure 4 and Figure 5.

Figure 4. Straight line braking maneuver. The black profile represents the vehicle longitudinal acceleration against the longitudinal position.

Figure 5. Turning maneuver. The graphs report the vehicle lateral and longitudinal position respectively on the y-axis and x-axis. Under the form of colored dots, the vehicle longitudinal acceleration is shown in the upper graph and the lateral acceleration in the lower graph.

The observed hub torque is compared against the reference signal simulated in IPG for both the driving manoeuvres. As shown in the Figure 6 and Figure 7, the Kalman filter provides an accurate observation of the hub torque for both the straight line braking and the turning manoeuvre. The hub torque estimation error can be quantified in terms of $RMSE$ (root mean square error) as follows:

$$RMSE = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{k=1}^n (T_{hub} - \hat{T}_{hub})^2}{n}} \quad (17)$$

where the hat specifies the reference signals from the simulation environment. In both the trials, the presented tool is capable to observe the hub torque with a $RMSE$ underneath 30Nm.

In summary, as previously sketched in Figure 1, the observer here presented requires information coming from the chassis accelerometers, the hub sensors and the brake pressure sensors, to provide an estimate of the hub torque for each wheel. Instead, the prediction part draws upon a tire model that must be fed with the actual tire vertical load, F_{z_i} , and wheels longitudinal, s_{L_i} , and side, s_{S_i} , slips. The state space formulation associated to the observer is rearranged in order to handle the hub torque as an augmented state [23]. Thereafter, it is trivial to evaluate the actual brake friction coefficient once the hub torque is observed, the clamping force is measured and the radial position of the clamping force application point is known.

Figure 6. Comparison between the simulated hub torque in IPG CarMaker (Reference) and the observed value (KF) for the straight line braking. Above the results for the front left wheel and below for the rear right wheel.

Figure 7. Comparison between the simulated hub torque in IPG CarMaker (Reference) and the observed value (KF) for the turning maneuver. Above the results for the front left wheel and below for the rear right wheel.

CONCLUSION

The possibility to predict online the friction coefficient for each brake of the vehicle is an important task for the control engineers aimed at designing more and more efficient controllers. Indeed, in the recent years, new control methodologies, mainly for electric vehicles, have been developed with the aim of improving the braking performance and the vehicle safety. The knowledge of the brake friction coefficient is useful to maintain the brake in the safe operating region, avoiding the fading, and to evaluate the actual braking torque for

the enhancement of vehicle control systems, such as ABS, ESP and TC, with simultaneous reduction of brake wear and particle emissions, and improvement of NVH [27].

The state observation technique for online estimation of the disc brakes friction coefficient has been presented as a novel tool since not investigated yet by the research community. In its intent, the state observer outperforms classical analytical methods and reveals suitable for online applications. Indeed, compared to the model based approach and neural networks, it uses measurement coming directly from the vehicle sensors by avoiding an analytical description of the brake phenomenology; it requires less computational burden and guarantees robustness and reliability against variations of the plant characteristics due to brake wear itself or in case of replacement with aftermarket brake linings.

Considering all the mentioned advantages and the achieved results, it appears clear that a state observer could be a very powerful tool for the online observation of the brakes friction coefficient. Hence, further research effort will be put in the design of an observer for non-homogeneous and unknown road conditions in order to improve the driving safety, during emergency braking, and to enhance the brake actuation, during service braking, with simultaneous reduction of the wear and PM emissions.

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